

Some Coordination Polymers[†]

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THERE has been a phenomenal growth in technology since the World War II and rapid strides had necessarily to be made in the sciences to meet the requirements of new materials with specific properties, in order to meet the demands of growing technology. This often led to discoveries on the border lines of different disciplines, which subsequently resulted in the development of investigations of inter-disciplinary interests. During this period, inorganic chemistry underwent a renaissance and the frontiers of the subject began expanding. The chemistry of polymers which had by now already advanced sufficiently, provided an impetus for the study of a new class of compounds known as inorganic polymers.

Polymer, in general, can be defined as a substance in which many structural units are connected by valence bonds in any possible way. On the basis of this definition, inorganic polymers would include a variety of substances, like mortar, natural silicates, quartz, polyphosphates, polyphosphazenes, glasses, diamond, graphite, polymeric boron nitride, sulphur nitrides, silicones and even ionic crystal aggregates like sodium chloride. Various organometallic and metal-organic substances are often included in inorganic polymers. The oldest synthetic inorganic polymer, in fact the oldest of all synthetic polymers—was a simple alkali silicate glass used during the Badarian period in Egypt (*ca* 12 000 B.C.) used as a glaze in ornamental amulets and beads. Subsequent improvements in glass manufacture continued through centuries and reached a stage of perfection¹ during the time of Tutankhamen (1 300 B.C.). The next major discovery in the area of inorganic polymers occurred about 3000 years later when Thomas Graham² published an account of obtaining sodium polyphosphates both in crystalline and amorphous forms.

The conventional polymers with an organic backbone are characterised by high viscosity and long range elasticity, useful for their applications in technology, but they suffer from a disadvantage that most of them break down on heating in air below 250°. On oxidation, the carbon and hydrogen oxidise to CO₂ and H₂O. Commercial products, like polyethylene, polyamide, polyester fibres, *etc.* are popular examples of organic polymers. It may be pointed out that the important Ziegler-Natta catalyst used for polymerising ethylene is the inorganic species containing Ti^{III}. The high-density polyethylene so formed, is relatively hard, stiff and

consists of mainly straight chains. However, the inherent flammability of the above commercial products is a great disadvantage. The Summerland disaster in the Isle of Man on 2 August 1973 caused great concern about the desirability of such materials for household use. Inorganic polymers, on the other hand are thermally more stable and are therefore suitable for withstanding high temperatures. Moreover, they are stronger, harder, usually insoluble, but are brittle.

The term coordination polymer includes a variety of substances, and in general, can be defined as a macromolecular entity involving a metallic element which forms an integral part of the backbone. It is usual to classify the coordination polymers in this way.

The study of coordination polymers which was systematically initiated nearly four decades ago is now regarded as one of the developing frontier areas of coordination chemistry. Renewed interest has been evinced in the context of obtaining materials with high temperature resistance. The potential applications of coordination polymers are as surface coatings on metals and glasses, adhesives, high temperature lubricants, electrical insulators, semiconductors, heat shields for artificial satellite and space ships, nose cones of missiles, constructional materials in aerospace industry and space vehicle and in various other projects. Attempts are also being made to obtain polymer fibre with special properties and has been successfully tried for communication system in some countries.

The synthesis of a coordination polymer is usually achieved by one of the following procedures : (i) a metal complex may yield a polymeric material during its formation due to the favourable donor groups present in the ligand, (ii) the ligand itself be a preformed organic polymer to which a metal ion may suitably be coordinated, and (iii) a metal ion may be coordinated with a ligand, and the monomeric metal complex reacted with another organic compound to form a polymeric complex.

In the author's laboratory, interest in the field of coordination polymers arose out of the exploration of stable polymeric materials. This led to the synthesis of several novel types of organic monomers which were used further for polymerisation with a metal ion. The ligands employed were hydroxy- and amino-anthraquinones, phthalein dyes, azo dyes with 8-quinolinol units, and Schiff bases. Some

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work on polymeric metal complexes of Mannich bases has also been done.

Frank *et al.*³ initiated the work on metal complexes of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone. Kanda and Saito⁴ prepared 1:1 polymeric complexes of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}. An interesting feature observed by physical measurements revealed that Cu^{II} polymers are rigid rods⁵. Jain and Singhal⁶ were able to prepare a three-dimensional polymer with Zr^{IV}. Thermal studies of these polymers were carried out by Bottei and Frangman⁷. Naphthazarin and quinizarin, however, form six-membered rings. Bailes and Calvin⁸ assigned polymeric octahedral structure to Co^{II} naphthazarin complex.

(1) 2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone

(2) 5,8-Dihydroxy-1,4-naphthazarin (Naphthazarin)

Polymeric chelates of 1,4- and 1,5-dihydroxyanthraquinone (1,4-DHA, 1,5-DHA) were prepared by Guggiari⁹ and Mangini and Stratta¹⁰, respectively.

(3) 1,4-DHA

(4) 1,5-DHA

Coble and Holzclaw¹¹ synthesised chelate polymers of Cu^{II} with various dihydroxyquinoid ligands and compared their respective thermal stabilities on the basis of increased number of rings. Bottei and McEachen¹² compared the ir spectra and thermal stability of chloroanilic and bromoanilic acid polymers and those of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (1). Copper chelates were found to be most

(5) Chloroanilic acid

(6) Bromoanilic acid

stable and zinc chelates least thermally stable. The order of stability of polymers of ligands were

chloroanilic acid > bromoanilic acid > 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone. The same authors¹² also synthesised complexes of copper and cobalt with juglone, 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and naphthazarin, and attempted to establish a relationship between thermal stability and polymeric structure or ring size. Coordination polymers of tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and rhodizonic acid were reported by Bottei and Greene¹⁴. Metals chosen were copper, cobalt, nickel and zinc. Except copper which forms Cu₂L, other metals yield complexes of the composition M₂L.6H₂O. The order of thermal stability for tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and rhodizonic acid chelates are Co > Zn > Ni > Pb > Cu and Ni > Zn > Co > Pb > Cu, respectively. Bottei and Quane¹⁵ investigated the thermal stability of polymers from β-hydronaphthazarin as opposed to polymers from naphthazarin and attributed the decrease in stability of the former to the decrease in electron delocalisation and aromaticity in the ring system. Similarly, Bottei and Frangman¹⁶ attributed the lack of stability of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone chelates essentially to the same reason, as well as to the formation of a five rather than a six-membered ring. However, on these assumptions, the relative thermal stabilities of tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and rhodizonic acid chelates could not be established. Bottei and Frangman¹⁷ synthesised coordination polymers of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone with copper, nickel and zinc. Copper formed CuL, but other metals

(7) Tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone

(8) Rhodizonic acid

form polymers of the general composition ML.2H₂O. The order of decreasing thermal stability is Zn > Co ~ Ni > Cu.

Maurya *et al.*¹⁸ have initiated systematic study on coordination polymers from these laboratories and synthesised by refluxing ethanolic solutions of salicylamide (SAM) with Mn^{II}, ZrO^{IV}, UO₂^{VI} and Be^{II}. SAM acts as tridentate ligand although all the three donor sites are not coordinated to the same metal ion. Two SAM ions are bonded to each metal ion through the hydroxyl and carbonyl oxygens. The metal ion is linked to two such groups by the coordination through the nitrogen of the NH₂ groups leading to a polymeric structure 9 (except Be complex).

(9) Bis(salicylamido)metal complex

Coordination polymers of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone with Hg^{II} , ZrO^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} and of 1,5-dihydroxyanthraquinone with Be^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , ZrO^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} ions have been investigated by the same workers. The compounds are stable, powdery in appearance, and insoluble in water, dilute mineral acids, alkalis, and in most of the common organic solvents. They are brown in colour except that uranium complexes are dark blue black. The DTA, DTG and TG thermograms indicate that the heat effect is endothermic, which reveals the sublimation of the ligands. The order of thermal stability is $\text{UO}_2(390^\circ) > \text{ZrO}(360^\circ) > \text{Hg}(340^\circ)$ in the case of quinizarin, and $\text{Mn}(380^\circ) > \text{Be}(370^\circ) > \text{UO}_2(360^\circ) > \text{ZrO}(350^\circ) > \text{Cd}(300^\circ) > \text{Hg}(285^\circ)$ in the case of anthrarufine. The composition of the polymers is $\text{ML} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, however, Be^{II} polymer is ML . These have been assigned octahedral polymeric structure, on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, and reflectance spectra and thermal study.

Coordination polymers of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with 1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxyanthraquinone have been reported by Banerjee and Dey¹⁰. These have been prepared by homocondensation of ligand and metal acetate hydrates in DMF. Dark blue to black products obtained were amorphous solids, insoluble in practically all common organic solvents indicative of their polymeric structure. Due to their insoluble nature molecular weight determination was not possible. One-to-one metal to ligand ratio was found as expected for chain polymers. Association of $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ per metal was established through elemental analysis, ir spectra and thermal analysis. Magnetic and spectral measurements assigned octahedral geometry around central metal.

John and Dey²⁰ have synthesised coordination polymers of some bipoisitive transition metals with 1,4- and 1,5-diaminoanthraquinone. The order of thermal stability for 1,4- and 1,5-diaminoanthraquinone complexes are $\text{Co}(350^\circ) > \text{Cu}(300^\circ) > \text{Ni}(280^\circ) > \text{Mn}(260^\circ)$; and $\text{Cu}(360^\circ) > \text{Ni}(320^\circ) > \text{Co}(280^\circ) > \text{Mn}(250^\circ)$, respectively. The elucidation of their structures reveal that complexation occurs through phenolic oxygen and quinolic oxygen as indicated by ir spectra, and the polymeric chain grows.

(10) 1,2,5,8-Tetrahydroxyanthraquinone

(11) 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

(12) 1,5-Diaminoanthraquinone

Metal complexes of 8-quinolinol are among the most stable coordination compounds involving organic ligands. Several coordination polymers have been prepared by using ligands of bis(8-quinolinol) type. Adachi²¹ and Kawai *et al.*²² studied the metallic polymers of 5,8-dihydroxy quinoxaline. 1:1 Polymeric chelates of 1,4- and 1,6-dihydroxyphenazines were synthesised by Kidani²³ and Berg and Alam²⁴.

(13) 5,8-Dihydroxyquinoxaline

(14) 1,4-Dihydroxyphenazine

(15) 1,6-Dihydroxyphenazine

Bailar *et al.*²⁵ synthesised a number of coordination polymers of bis(8-hydroxyquinolines). The thermal stability of the copper and zinc bis(8-quinolinol) type coordination polymers were examined by heating the sample in a stream of nitrogen and measuring the weight loss. The bis(8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)sulphone ligand appeared to give the most stable coordinated systems with decomposition temperature of 280° and 320° for the copper and zinc polymers, respectively. Korshak *et al.*²⁶ followed the pattern of Bailar and reported

the synthesis of a number of coordination polymers of bis(8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)methane as well as a number of mixed polymers. The thermal stability of a group of the first row transition metal coordination homopolymers was elucidated by noting colour changes as the sample was heated in air in a capillary tube, and also by measuring deformation of the sample with increasing temperature. Berg and Alam²⁷ discussed the synthesis of coordination polymers of 8,8'-dihydroxy-5,5'-biquinolol, and the use of ligand as an analytical reagent for detecting metal ions in the microgram range. Metals like copper, zinc, cobalt, nickel, manganese and cadmium were employed. They also studied the thermal stability of these polymers by heating the samples at different temperatures in air and observing changes in colour and in infrared spectra.

(16) Bis(8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)methane
X = OH₂⁺ - sulphone; X = SO₂

(17) 8,8'-Dihydroxy, 5,5'-biquinolol

Poddar and Saha²⁸ have prepared polymeric complexes of some transition metal ions with Schiff base derived from 5-formylloxine and *p*-phenylenediamine.

(18) 5-Formylloxine-phenylenediamine

Banerjee and Dey²⁹ reported a new approach to link two molecules of 8-quinolol by coupling it with tetraazonium chlorides of *p*-phenylenediamine, benzidine and *o*-dianisidine, respectively. Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} form coordination polymers with the quadrifunctional dyes³⁰.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(19) Quinolol Schiff bases

These complexes were prepared by refluxing ligand and metal acetate hydrate in dimethylsulphoxide. Dark red brown complexes are amorphous and insoluble in practically all common organic solvents. The 1:1 metal to ligand ratio and association of 2H₂O per metal ion is inferred. These are octahedral and decompose at high temperature. The order of thermal stability for the complexes of dyes from *p*-phenylenediamine, benzidine, and *o*-dianisidine is Cd(380°) > Mn(320°) > Zn(300°) ~ Fe(300°) > Co(280°) ~ Ni(280°) > Cu(260°); Cd(360°) ~ Zn(360°) > Mn(340°) > Co(320°) ~ Ni(320°) ~ Cu(320°) > Fe(300°); and Cd(400°) > Zn(380°) > Mn(360°) ~ Cu(360°) > Fe(340°) > Co(320°) > Ni(300°). The thermal stability of the complexes of dyes shows the order *p*-phenylenediamine < benzidine < *o*-dianisidine. This may be attributed to the increasing size of the amine moiety.

2-Carboxyphenyl-5-azo-8-hydroxyquinoline and 5,5'-(benzidinebisazo)salicylaldoxime have also been employed for the synthesis of coordination polymers of transition metals. Octahedral com-

(20) 2-Carboxyphenyl-5-azo-8-hydroxyquinoline

plexes show the following order of thermal stability: Co(340°) ~ Cu(340°) > Ni(320°); Cd(420°) > Zn(360°) ~ Mn(360°) > Co(340°) > Ni(320°) > Cu(300°).

(21) 5,5'-(Benzidinebisazo)salicylaldoxime

Agarwal *et al.*²¹ have prepared the complexes of fluorescein with Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ce^{III} , Th^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} at pH 3.0-4.0 and no hydroxo groups or bridges have been found to be present.

Magnetic study has been made for Co^{II} complex which is paramagnetic, whereas other complexes are largely diamagnetic. The effective magnetic moment value for Co^{II} complex has been found to be 4.77 B.M. The theoretical values for various geometries have been shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THEORETICAL VALUES OF MAGNETIC MOMENT FOR Co^{II} COMPLEXES

Geometry	Permissible values B.M.
Octahedral	4.7—5.2
Tetrahedral	4.4—4.8
Square planar	4.8—5.2

The observed magnetic moment value is at the lower limit of octahedral complexes and at the upper limit for tetrahedral complexes. However, the observed μ_{eff} value is similar to some other Co^{II} complexes having distorted square-pyramidal geometry. Structure of fluorescein and its study of the complexes reveal that all the three possible donor sites are involved in coordination. Evidently, since chelation is not possible for steric reasons, this type of complexation results in a three-dimensional coordinated polymeric structure. This polymerisation produces properties of insolubility in common organic solvents and high thermal stability, which is in the order $\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}(460^\circ) > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}(360^\circ) > \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}(340^\circ) \sim \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}(340^\circ) > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}}(32^\circ) \sim \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(320^\circ) > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(260^\circ) \sim \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(260^\circ)$.

(22) Fluorescein (Na-salt)

Complexes of Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Th^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} with disodium salt of eosin have similarly been prepared. Its study of the ligand suggests that no single structure hitherto assigned to it, represent the true state of affairs and six resonating structures have been proposed²².

Although complexes of eosin appear to be polymeric and exhibit insolubility in common organic solvents and high thermal stability, the composition of the complexes of eosin and fluorescein differ. Also Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes probably have distorted octahedral geometry and are magnetically normal in behaviour. Order of thermal stability of the complexes is $\text{Cd}(360^\circ) > \text{Fe}(350^\circ) > \text{UO}_2(300^\circ) \sim \text{Th}(300^\circ) \sim \text{Pb}(300^\circ) > \text{Cu}(290^\circ)$.

(23) Eosin and its resonating structures

Pfeiffer and Pfitzner²³ were the first to study bis(Schiff bases) as catenating ligands. They investigated copper derivative of bis(Schiff bases) derived from diamines and salicylaldehyde which gave cryoscopic molecular weights corresponding to dimers. But later these were given a polymeric structure, since the established dimers were soluble.

Schiff base metal complexes as ligands have been described in a review by Sinn and Harris²⁴. Copper(II) complex derived from *N,N'*-1,2-propylene-bis(salicylalimine) reacts with copper perchlorate to form the trinuclear complex.

(24) *N,N'*-1,2-Propylene-bis(salicylalimine)copper(II)

Oxygen-bridged polymeric forms of bis(*N*-methyl-salicylalimino)nickel(II) (24) have been isolated in the solid state by Harris *et al.*²⁵ which are paramagnetic. A corresponding copper(II) analogue is also known which exists in both monomeric and dimeric forms and the metal atoms are linked by oxygen bridges²⁶.

(25) Bis(*N*-methylsalicylaldimino)nickel(II)

(26) Bis(*N*-methylsalicylaldimino)copper(II)

Bailar *et al.*³⁷ investigated thiopicolinamide, and

(27) Thiopicolinamide

ketoimides were investigated by Nesmeyanov *et al.*³⁸. The analytical data for thiopicolinamide based

(28) Ketoimides

polymers with Cu, Ni or Zn metals indicate molecular weights over 5000. The powdery products are thermally stable to 250-410°. Cu^{II} polymer of ketoimide was prepared by homocondensation in DMF or by interfacial condensation technique between chlorobenzene and aqueous solution. The resultant powders were stable upto 400° for *p*-phenylenediamine and to 350° for benzidine.

Thiosemicarbazides, thiosemicarbazones and their derivatives possess various biological activities and are extensively used in the treatment of tuberculosis. Antimicrobial and antitumour activity are also shown by thiosemicarbazones. Their activity is thought to be due to their ability to form chelates with trace metals present in living systems^{39,40}.

Drinkard and Chakravarty⁴¹ prepared bis-(thiosemicarbazones) of terephthalaldehyde and naphthazarin and its polymeric Zn^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The coordination polymers of isoterphthalaldehyde-bis(thiosemicarbazone) and terephthalaldehyde-bis(thiosemicarbazone) with Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} have been synthesised by Marcu and Dima⁴², and their thermal properties and semi-conducting properties were studied.

(29) Terephthalaldehyde-bis(thiosemicarbazone)

(30) Isoterphthalaldehyde-bis(thiosemicarbazone)

Thioamide⁴³ with variously substituted benzene rings were employed for the preparation of polymers. Zinc complexes with quadridentate Schiff bases of

(31) Thioamide

salicylaldehyde and polymethylenediamine with 2-9 carbon atoms chain have been investigated in

(32) Salicylaldehyde(polymethylenediamine)

detail⁴⁴. Chelating polyesters with azomethine linkage have been synthesised⁴⁵. Suk *et al.*⁴⁶ have

(33) Polyesters with azomethine linkage

prepared transition metal polymers such as poly [M(II)-ethylenediaminequinizarin], where M=Co, Ni and Cu. X-Ray powder method of analysis shows these to be of low molecular weight, and these were found to be insoluble in ether, benzene or acetone.

(34) Polyethylenediaminequinizarin

Marcu and Dima⁴⁷ investigated the polycoordination of dimethyl-4,4'-[p-phenylenebis(methylidene nitrito)]disalicylate with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in DMF. The coloured polymers were found to be heat stable and semiconducting, and were amorphous, only Cu^{II} polymer having a crystallinity of 89%. The ir and esr spectra of the complexes were studied to elucidate the polymeric nature.

(35) Dimethyl-4,4'-[p-phenylene-bis(methylidene nitrito)]disalicylate

Maurya *et al.*⁴⁸ synthesised coordination chain polymers of terephthalaldehyde-bis(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone) with Be^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO₂^{VI} ions by homocondensation in DMF. The variously coloured complexes Be (yellow), Co (reddish brown), Ni (reddish brown), Cu (greenish yellow), Cd (dark yellow), Zn (red) and UO₂ (yellow) were powdery in appearance, and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. Co, Ni, Cu and UO₂ complexes are octahedral while those of Be, Zn and Cd are tetrahedral. Ir spectral studies suggest coordination through thioenolic S and azomethine N. They decompose at 260-360°, the order of stability being Ni > Cd ~ Be > Co ~ Cu ~ UO₂.

(36) Terephthalaldehyde-bis(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone)

Terephthalaldehyde-bis(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone) [TPBPTS] acts as tetradentate chelating agent coordinating through the thioenolic sulphur and nitrogen of the (C=N) group of the Schiff base. Polymerisation is achieved since steric factors prevent the coordination of all the donor groups to a single metal ion, and the metal ion acts as a bridging unit between two donor groups of the ligand. Thus the polymeric chain grows through the consecutive TPBPTS-metal linkage. The polymeric chelate is neutral, since the protons from the SH groups remain ionised.

Macarovici *et al.*⁴⁹ prepared Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from resorcyaldehyde and bis(4-aminophenyl)methane or 4,4'-biaminobiphenyl.

(37) Resorcyaldehyde-bis(4-aminophenyl)methane

(38) Resorcyaldehyde-bis(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)

Polyazomethine, the polymeric Schiff base ligand was synthesised by Dubský *et al.*⁵⁰ and thus established a new approach for preparing coordination polymers.

(39) Polyazomethine

Polymeric Schiff bases with long chain and high molecular weight were prepared by Aspey⁵¹, and also by Marvel *et al.*⁵². Initial compounds had been salicylaldehyde, and o-phenylenediamine, but two different pathways had been adopted.

(a)

(40) Formation of salicylaldehyde(*p*-phenylenediamine)

(41) Long chain Schiff bases and their polymeric metal complexes

Bis(Schiff base) has been prepared from terephthalaldehyde and anthranilic acid and its complexes with bivalent metals have been synthesised by Singh *et al.*⁵³. The octahedral 1 : 1 polymers are thermally stable and decompose in the order Cd(460°) > Mg(420°) ~ Zn(420°) ~ Pb(420°) > Ni(400°) ~ Co(400°) > Mn(360°) > Cu(300°).

Polymeric complexes of Schiff bases of salicylaldehyde and *p*-phenylenediamine or benzidine were investigated by Maurya *et al.*⁵⁴. Salicylaldehydato-metal complexes were condensed with the diamines in DMF, with the bivalent metal ions, like Be, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, and UO₂. They are amorphous solids and are insoluble.

The values of the magnetic moments show that the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic and Ni^{II} complexes diamagnetic. The geometry of the complexes along with their thermal decomposition temperature are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GEOMETRY, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF BIS(SALICYLALDEHYDATO) METAL(II)-1,4-DIAMINOBENZENE COMPLEXES

Geometry	Magnetic moment B.M.	Decomp. temp. °C
Co ^{II} Tetrahedral	4.48	320
Ni ^{II} Sq.-planar	Diamag.	350
Cu ^{II} Sq.-planar	1.85	340
Be ^{II} ...	Diamag.	400
Zn ^{II} ...	Diamag.	400
Cd ^{II} ...	Diamag.	340

Tetrahedral geometry around the central metal is suggested except in the case of Cu and Ni, which are square-planar, while UO₂ complex is octahedral.

Order of thermal stability for *p*-phenylenediamine bases is Be(400°) ~ Zn(400°) > Co(340°) ~ Ni(340°) ~ Cd(340°) ~ UO₂(340°) > Cu(320°), and for benzidine base it is Ni(400°) > Cu(360°) ~ Cd(360°) > UO₂(340°) > Co(320°).

(42) Salicylaldehydodiamines

Singh *et al.*⁵⁵ have investigated in detail the syntheses of coordination polymers of terephthalaldehyde-bis(semicarbazone) and bis(isonicotinic acid hydrazone). Ethanolic NaOH solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride was added to ethanolic solution of terephthalaldehyde and refluxed to get a yellow precipitate of the Schiff base. The terephthalaldehyde bis(isonicotinic acid hydrazone) was prepared in ethanolic solution. The polymeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were prepared by homocondensation in DMF. The coloured amorphous solids are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. Elemental analysis suggests 1 : 1 metal to ligand ratio and an association of 2H₂O per metal ion. Its spectra suggests coordination in

(43) Tautomeric forms of terephthalaldehyde-bis(isonicotinic acid hydrazone)

enolic form though ligand exists in keto form. Octahedral geometry around central metal has been established. The stability order for semicarbazone is Cd(340°) ~ Zn(340°) > Ni(320°) > Co(300°) > Cu(220°), and that for isonicotinic acid hydrazone is Zn(420°) > Cd(400°) > Co(380°) > Ni(300°) ~ Cu(300°).

(44) Terephthalaldehyde-bis(semicarbazone)

(45) Terephthalaldehyde-(isonicotinic acid)hydrazone
 $[X = OH, COO^-]$

Maurya *et al.*⁵⁶ have carried out polymerisation reactions involving the formation of Schiff base metal complexes by condensation of terephthalaldehyde with benzoic or nicotinic acid hydrazides. All the complexes are paramagnetic except Zn^{II} and chelation occurs through the enolic form.

Copper and cobalt polymeric complexes of Schiff base derived from terephthalaldehyde and *m*-aminophenol have been prepared by Singh *et al.*⁵⁵

(46) Terephthalaldehyde(aminophenol)

Dwivedi⁵⁷ has synthesised a number of coordination polymers by employing Schiff bases derived from aromatic diamines, like *p*-phenylenediamine, benzidine and *o*-dianisidine, and phenolic aldehyde like 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The polymeric complexes were synthesised by refluxing an equimolar mixture of ligand and metal ion in DMF. The orders of thermal stability for these complexes are : bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-*o*-dianisidine, $Zn(380^\circ) > Mn(340^\circ) > Co(300^\circ) \sim Ni(300^\circ) \sim Cu(300^\circ) > UO_2(280^\circ)$; bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)benzidine, $Mn(380^\circ) > Ni(320^\circ) \sim Co(320^\circ) > Cu(300^\circ)$; and bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine, $Mn(340^\circ) > Ni(300^\circ) \sim Cu(300^\circ) > Co(280^\circ)$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(47) Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)diamines

Oxalyldihydrazone of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was prepared by refluxing oxalyldihydrazone and the phenolic aldehyde in the ratio of 1 : 2 in ethanolic DMF (4 : 1). This yellow hydrazone is dissolved in ammoniacal DMF and the solution of metal ions added to it to obtain coloured complexes. The complexes have distorted octahedral geometry around the central metal and are thermally stable. The order of thermal stability being $Zn(400^\circ) \sim Ni(400^\circ) > Co(320^\circ) \sim Cu(320^\circ)$.

(48) 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde oxalyldihydrazone

Pandey⁵⁸ synthesised polymeric metal complexes of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Fe^{II} and UO_2^{VI} with N^1 -(4-bromophenyl)- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide by refluxing ligand and metal (1 : 1) in DMF. Various coloured octahedral complexes are thermally stable and decompose in the order, $Zn(335^\circ) > Mn(300^\circ) > Cd(290^\circ) \sim Cu(290^\circ) > Fe(277^\circ) > Co(275^\circ) > Pb(270^\circ) \sim Ni(270^\circ) > UO_2(245^\circ)$. Coordination polymers of

bipositive metal ions with N^1 -allyl- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide were prepared by the same procedure. These decompose in the order, Zn(245°) > Cd(240°) > Ni(225°) ~ Cu(225°) > Co(220°) > Pb(205°). Dwivedi⁸⁷ has prepared polymeric metal complexes of N^1 -(4-chlorophenyl)- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide. The order of thermal stability for these complexes is Cu(300°) ~ Ni(300°) > Co(260°) ~ Zn(260°) ~ UO₂(260°) > Mn(240°) > Fe(200°).

(49) N^1 -(4-Bromophenyl)- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazone

(50) N^1 -(4-Chlorophenyl)- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazone

(51) N^1 -Allyl- N^4 -(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazone

Mannich bases as ligands which have not been used so far for the synthesis of polymeric metal complexes have recently been employed for the preparation of coordination polymers of some bipositive transition metal ions in these laboratories. Gupta⁸⁹ has exploited Mannich bases derived from hydroquinone, formaldehyde, dimethylamine, benzylamine or dibenzylamine. Khanna⁹⁰ used N,N' -bis(salicylamidomethyl)piperazine for the preparation of polymeric complexes.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(52) Mannich bases

(53) Mannich bases

Gupta⁸⁹ has investigated several Schiff bases derived from naphthaldehyde, Mannich base and bipositive metal complexes of oxalic and biscyclohexylidene hydrazide. On the basis of analytical, magnetic, thermal, diffuse reflectance and infrared spectral studies, following octahedral structure has been suggested for naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone complexes.

(54) Naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone complex

Mannich bases as potential polydentate ligands have been described by Gupta *et al.*⁸¹. They are synthesised by condensing hydroquinone, formaldehyde and benzylamine in dioxan medium. The polymeric metal complexes formed have the formula [ML₂.2H₂O]_n. The ir spectral data show that the ligand acts as tetradentate chelating agent, coordinating through phenolic oxygens and imino nitrogens. All the four donors do not coordinate to the same metal ion due to steric factors, thus leading to the formation of polymeric chain of ligand-metal linkages.

(55) 2,5-Bis(benzylaminomethyl)hydroquinone (Mannich base)

Khanna⁶⁰ and Dey *et al.*⁶² synthesised several polydentate ligands for the first time involving thiosemicarbazides, hydrazones and aldimines. 1-Thioformanilido-4-allylthiosemicarbazone (TFATS) displays nine tautomeric forms. It behaves as hexadentate ligand coordinating through thioenol, sulphur and two nitrogen atoms (N₁, N₆).

(56) 1-Thioformanilido-4-allylthiosemicarbazone

1-Isonicotinoyl- and 1-*p*-nitrobenzoyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazone (INATS, NBATS) behave as tetradentate ligands, coordinating through the thiole sulphur and nitrogen atoms. Steric factors prevent the coordination of all the donors to a single metal ion, which therefore, acts as a bridging unit between the donor sites of the ligand and thus the polymeric chain grows through consecutive INATS or NBATS metal linkages.

(57) 1-*p*-Nitrobenzoyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazone

A prominent extra band is observed at 880 cm⁻¹ due to NO₂ substituent present in benzene ring.

The aldimines are synthesised from 4,4'-methylene dianiline and salicylaldehyde.

(58) Di-salicylidene-4,4'-methylenedianiline

Schiff base is indicated by the appearance of C=N stretching band in the region 1625-20 cm⁻¹. The coordination occurs through the azomethine nitrogen and oxygen atom of phenolic group.

Esr spectral studies have been done for copper(II) complexes, and the esr parameters were determined. From the *g* values it has been inferred that d_{x²-y²} is in the ground state, which is in conformity with band assignments in the reflectance spectra.

μ_{eff} values were also determined by substituting *g*, *g*_{||} and *g*_⊥ obtained from esr spectra for monomeric copper(II) complexes by the following equation,

$$\mu_{\text{eff}}^2 = \frac{g_{\parallel}^2}{4} + \frac{g_{\perp}^2}{2} + \frac{3KT}{\lambda_0}(g-2)$$

The values are found to be in close agreement with those obtained by magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Singh and Misra⁶³ studied polymeric 2:1 metal-ligand complexes formed by thiophene-2-aldehydeoxalyldihydrazone with bivalent cations. The analytical data indicate the composition to be [M₂L.4H₂O]_n. The structure has been shown as 59 and two water molecules are attached to each metal ion.

(59) Thiophene-2-aldehydeoxalyldihydrazone

The studies have also been extended employing semithio-, 4-phenylthio-semicarbazides, nicotinic or isonicotinic hydrazides with thiophene-2-aldehyde.

Singh⁶⁴ has studied systematically the metal complexes formed by 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde (vanillin) with nicotinic, benzoic or salicylic acid hydrazides. Oxobridged complexes are formed by 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde salicylic acid hydrazone which are supported from ir spectral studies and lower magnetic moment values presumably due to metal-metal interaction.

(60) 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehydesalicylic acidhydrazone

In this brief account of some coordination polymers (summarised in the Appendix) an attempt has been made to draw the attention of workers to this interesting area of inorganic chemistry. It is hoped that further rigorous studies would provide a wealth of information on the various facets of these compounds and their industrial and biological applications.

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APPENDIX

SUMMARY OF STUDIES IN THE AUTHOR'S LABORATORY

Sl	Ligand	Metal	Ref
1	<i>N'</i> -(4-Bromophenyl)- <i>N'</i> -3,5-dinitrobenzoylthiosemicarbazone	Fe ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	58
2.	<i>N</i> -Allyl- <i>N'</i> -(3,5-dinitrobenzoylthiosemicarbazone)	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	58
2a.	Isatin thiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	67
3.	<i>N'</i> -(4-Chlorophenyl)- <i>N'</i> -3,5 dinitrobenzoylthiosemicarbazone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	57
3a	Vanillin thiosemicarbazone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	67
4.	1-Thioformanilido-4-allylthiosemicarbazone	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	62
5.	1-Isonicotinyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	60
6.	1- <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	60
7.	Naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	59
7a	Furfuraldehyde thiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	67
8.	Thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	68
9.	Anisaldehyde thiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	65
10.	Pyridine-2-carboxaldehydethiosemicarbazone	Ni ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	65
11	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene phenylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
12.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
13.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone)	Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Be ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	48
14	Thiophene-2-aldehyde 4-phenylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	63
15.	Anisaldehyde 4-phenylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	65
16.	Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde-4 phenylthiosemicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	65
17.	Salicylaldehyde semicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Be ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	18
17a	Isatin semicarbazone	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	67
18.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(semicarbazone)	Mn ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	55

19	Naphthaldehyde semicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	59
19a	Vanillin semicarbazone	Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II}	67
20.	Thiophene-2-aldehyde semicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	68
21.	Salicylidene-4-phenyl semicarbazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	58
22	Di 4-bromosalicylidene oxalyldihydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	58
23	Di-(2-hydroxy)-1-naphthalidene oxalyldihydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	57
24	Naphthaldehyde oxalyl dihydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	59
25	Thiophene-2-aldehyde oxalyldihydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	68
26	Furfuraldehyde oxalyldihydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	65
*26a.	Furfuraldehyde dianisidine		68
*26b.	Thiophene-2-aldehyde dianisidine		68
27.	Disalicylidene dianisidine	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	58
28.	Di-4-bromosalicylidene dianisidine	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	58
*28a	Ani-aldehyde dianisidine		68
29.	Di(2-hydroxy)1-naphthalidene dianisidine	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	57
30	Di(4-bromosalicylidene <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
31	Di(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
*31a	Anisaldehyde- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine		68
32.	Salicylidene- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	54
33	Salicylidenediamine	Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Be ^{II}	54
*33a	Thiophene-2-aldehyde- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine		68
34	Di-5-bromosalicylidene-4,4'-methylenedianiline	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	60
35	Di salicylidene-4,4'-methylenedianiline	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	60
36	Di-2-hydroxy-naphthalidene-4,4'-methylene dianiline	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	60
*36a	Furfuraldehyde <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine		68
37.	(4-Bromosalicylidene)-benzidine	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
*37a	Anisaldehydebenzidine		68
b	Thiophene-2-aldehydebenzidine		
c	Furfuraldehydebenzidine		
38.	Di(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)benzidine	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	57
39.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	57
40.	Salicylidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ VI	55

DEY : SOME COORDINATION POLYMERS

41.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	60	63.	Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	65
42.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(<i>p</i> -nitrobenzoic acid)-hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	60	64.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64
43.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (<i>p</i> -nitrobenzoic acid)-hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	60	65.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde (salicylic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64
44.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (benzoic acid)hydrazone	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	66.	Oxalic acid bis(cyclohexylidene)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	59
45.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde (benzoic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	67.	2-Hydroxynaphthalidene 4-amino-2-nitrotoluol	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	60
46.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (<i>o</i> -nitrobenzoic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	68.	(i) 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone, (ii) 1,5-diaminoanthraquinone, (iii) 1-aminoanthraquinone, (iv) 1,4- <i>N,N'</i> -dimethylaminoanthraquinone, (v) <i>N</i> -salicylideneanthranilic acid	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	20
47.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde- (<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	69.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(anthranilic acid)	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	53
48.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde (<i>o</i> -nitro benzoic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	70.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(<i>o</i> -aminophenol)	Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	50
49.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde (<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	71.	Salicylamide	Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Be ^{II} , ZrO ₄ ^{IV} , Hg ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	18
50.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde (<i>p</i> -nitrobenzoic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	72.	Dihydroxyanthraquinone	Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Be ^{II} , ZrO ₄ ^{IV} , Hg ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	18
51.	(i) Terephthaldehyde-bis-(benzoic acid)hydrazone and (ii) terephthaldehyde-bis(nicotinic acid) hydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	56	73.	(i) 5,5'-(Benzidine-bisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline ; (ii) 5,5'-(<i>p</i> phenylenediamine bisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline ; (iii) 5,5'-(<i>o</i> -dianisidine bisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	30
52.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde(nicotinic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	74.	5,5'-(Benzidine-bisazo) salicylaldoxime	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	29
53.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzaldehyde (nicotinic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	64	75.	2-Carboxyphenyl-5-azo-8-hydroxyquinoline	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	29
54.	Thiophene-2-aldehyde (nicotinic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	63	76.	1,2,5,8-Tetrahydroxy-anthraquinone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	19
55.	Anisaldehyde (nicotinic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	65	77.	(i) <i>o</i> -Cresotic acid ; (ii) <i>m</i> -cresotic acid ; (iii) hydroxynaphthoic acid	Cu ^{II}	66
56.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy acetophenone (isonicotinic acid)hydrazone	Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	53	78.	Mixed ligand 1 : 1C-phenanthroline as primary, and <i>o</i> -cresotic acid and <i>m</i> -cresotic acid as secondary ligands	Fe ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	66
57.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	53	79.	Eosin	Fe ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Th ^{IV} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	32
58.	Terephthaldehyde-bis-(isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	55	80.	Fluorescein	Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Ce ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	31
59.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde (isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	60	* Metal complexes under investigation.			
59a.	Isatin (isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	67	<hr/>			
60.	Naphthaldehyde (isonicotinic acid)hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	59	References			
60a.	Vanillin (isonicotinic acid)hydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	67	1. N. H. RAY, "Inorganic Polymers", Academic Press, London, 1972.			
61.	Thiophene-2-aldehyde (isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{VI}	63	2. T. GRAHAM, <i>Philos. Trans.</i> , 1838, 123, 253.			
61a.	Furfuraldehyde(isonicotinic acid) hydrazone	Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	67	3. R. L. FRANK, G. R. CLARK and J. N. COKER, <i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i> 1950, 72, 1827.			
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